

SLANG AND ITS USAGE IN SOCIETY

Akhrorova Ruzikhon Usmanovna,

Ferghana State University,

PhD, senior teacher.

axrorova.prof@gmail.com

Komilova Muhayyo

Master`s degree student

Fergana state university

Annotation: This article studies about borrowings and slangs which are used in society frequently, in particular, the origin of jargons and slangs, their usage and scope of slangs in modern world.

Key words: Social networks, esthetic attitude, trend, vulgarism, jargon, slang, argo, unnatural environment, globalization.

The topic of social networks has recently become one of the most frequently mentioned and discussed topics in the press. It is not for nothing, of course. Because there are not a few people among us who are not at all interested in the meaning and importance of this concept, but at the same time have become "captives" of one or more of them, "wandering" aimlessly in the virtual world. However, it cannot be denied that, along with the positive aspects of social networks, there are also negative aspects that turn our moral and aesthetic views upside down and contradict our nationality.

For example, words from foreign languages or words that have no meaning but are "trending" in quotation marks, and words in the category of argo, are becoming popular very quickly through social networks. Many people confuse such networks with electronic mass media. It's not like that. Social networks must have legal status to reach the level of mass media. Otherwise, no matter how much information it spreads, it will remain a source of free information. In a number of

countries, social networks have been recognized as mass media. Of course, it is possible that social networks will be given the status of mass media in our country as well.

Nowadays, the trend that the colloquial language should not be overshadowed by the literary language is proving itself in the world. Spoken language is the main part of language, a living form that is always developing and enriching. It reflects the people's life and spirit. Therefore, the literary language should not displace it, it is necessary to leave areas where colloquial language is used. It has not been long since this term entered the society, but its synonym is known to everyone. Jargon. So, what kind of language style is it, is it correct to call it a language style?!

JARGON (French jargon. — nonsense) is a language of a social group that differs from the common colloquial language and local dialects with its own lexicon, phonetics, and grammar. Jargon occurs in a certain social environment and serves their interests (Jargon between students, military personnel, different professions). Such Jargons should not be confused with any professional language with highly developed and precise terminology. Jargon is both lexically and stylistically diverse, rapidly changing, and unstable. For instance, today there are so many jargons among Uzbek youth «*sirpandim*» instead of «*ketdim*», «*soqqa*» instead of «*pul*», «*ko'ki*» instead of «*dollar*»; among artists «*tom suvoq*» instead of «*xizmat uchun haq olmaslik*», «*yakan*» instead of «*pul*» and etc.

The emergence and spread of slang and argotism as slang is rightly assessed as a negative phenomenon in the development of the national language. Therefore, the language policy is to refuse to use them. However, writers and publicists have the right to refer to these vocabulary layers in search of realistic colors in describing relevant aspects of our reality. At the same time, jargons, argos, along with dialects, should be included in artistic speech only in the form of quotations. Parodists of the XXth century in various genres of spoken and written speech do not allow its qualities such as harmony and purity, accuracy, richness and expressiveness, comprehensibility and comfort for the receiver to be violated.

It is not known when the word slang first appeared in spoken English. It was first recorded in England in the 18th century. Then it means "insult". Approximately in 1850, the term came into wider use as a term for "illegal" colloquialism. At the same time, synonyms of the word slang appear - lingo, used mainly in the lower strata of society, and argot - preferred by the colored population.

The extent of the concept of "slang" is shown by its later descriptive definitions, for example, "lewd colloquial speech" or poetic "dithyramb" descriptions of slang as "a beat of the tongue" (D. Galsworthy); or "slang is the language of rolling up your sleeves, spitting into your palm and getting to work" (Karl. Sandburg), this "poem is a common man", etc. It is clear that in the scientific sense, such definitions are not very crucial, although they still show that jargon is considered a common language of the people and serves as a basis for creating a national dictionary.

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